

D2.1

First Compound submission report

Version 1.0 2025-08-31

Deliverable Report

Project title	IMPULSE – Improving user experience, long-term sustainability and services of EU-OPENSREEN
Grant Agreement No	101132028
Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-03
Call	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01 – (Consolidation of the RI landscape – Individual support for evolution and long-term sustainability of pan-European research infrastructure)
DG/Agency	Research Executive Agency
Deliverable number	2.1
Deliverable title	First Compound submission report
Lead beneficiary	USC
Contributing beneficiaries	EU-OS, UH, IMB PAN, IMG, HZI, UiO, DTU, LIOS, KI, i3S, CSIC, MEDINA
Author(s)	Victoria Mora, Mabel Loza, Geert Daudey, Pepo Brea
Type of deliverable	R – Report
Work package No.	2
Work package title	Creating a repository of community compounds
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Due date (in months)	M18 (August 2025)
Delivery date (actual)	31.08.2025
Description of deliverable	Progress report on compound submission and ambassador activities

Legal disclaimer

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Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 101132028. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable outlines the progress achieved under Work Package 2 (WP2) of the IMPULSE project, focusing on the expansion of EU-OPENSREEN's compound collections through active engagement of academic chemists and the establishment of a European Academic Compound Library (EACL). The goal of WP2 is to actively engage local chemistry researchers, encouraging them to make their compounds accessible to the biological research community through a regular, transparent framework, thereby enabling a wider community of biologists to test these compounds in suitable bioassays.

This deliverable report, covering the period from March 2024 (M1) to August 2025 (M18), outlines the mechanisms established for compound sourcing, details the outreach activities of the ambassador network, and describes the integration of new compound submissions into the central compound management system at EU-OPENSREEN.

2 Detailed report on the deliverable

2.1 Background/Introduction

The goal of the academic compound initiative is to **establish a transparent, collaborative framework that enables academic chemists to contribute compounds to the EU-OPENSSCREEN research infrastructure (RI)**. This initiative aims to expand and diversify the community compound library by incorporating previously inaccessible or novel chemical entities into one unique collection.

IMPULSE WP2 builds on the key achievements of the H2020 EU-OPENSSCREEN-DRIVE project,¹ including the development of a **compound registration platform** (Figure 1), the formation of an **academic library working group** of national ambassadors, and the collection of 5,677 **academic compounds** by March 2024.

eu:openscreen | COMPOUND SUBMISSION

A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6
B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6
C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6

DATA FOR THIS ENTRY:

Box_ID:

Box_Location: << >>

ViaI_Code:

Amount_mg: ? [(x).xxx mg]

Provider:

save as default provider:

Provider_Comp_ID:

(must be unique)

SAVE UNDO DELETE

(logged in as Dr. Edgar Specker, username: screening)

back to main page logout

Copy structure from GET

CLEAR EDITOR WINDOW

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Figure 1 Compound Registration Platform for compound submission to the EACL.

Located in Berlin, the **Central Compound Management Facility (CCMF)** of EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC receives compounds from chemists, assesses their purity and identity, reformats them, and then distributes them to EU-OPENSSCREEN screening partner sites² for further testing.

All academic compounds undergo **biological profiling**³ using a broad set of tests and assays including:

- Physicochemical property measurements, such as solubility.

¹EU-OPENSSCREEN-DRIVE (<https://drive.eu-openscreen.eu/>, Grant Agreement No 823893) is a Horizon 2020–funded project that extended the EU-OPENSSCREEN infrastructure—offering access to a Europe-wide network of screening and chemistry facilities, a compound library, database, and training services—to ensure long-term sustainability and enhance data re-use and innovation in chemical biology.

² <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/screening.html>

³ <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/bioprofiling-assays.html>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 101132028.

- Interference tests with common bioluminescence reporters.
- Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) detection assays.
- Cell viability assays.
- Antibacterial and antifungal activity assays.
- Advanced morphological profiling methods, such as cell painting assays.

Bioprofiling assays are run at the following EU-OPENSREEN partner sites: University of Santiago de Compostela (USC), Spain; Polish Academy of Sciences, Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry (IBCH PAS), Poland; Institute for Molecular Medicine (FIMM), Finland; Fundación MEDINA (MEDINA), Spain; Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research (HZI), Germany; Leibniz Institute for Molecular Pharmacology (FMP), Germany; and Palacký University Olomouc, Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry (IMTM), Czech Republic.

Additionally, compounds are available at EU-OPENSREEN screening sites to be used in a wide range of **screening projects**, depending on the researcher's needs.

Screening and bioprofiling data are uploaded to the **European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD)**⁴⁵ with an embargo period of six months to three years, depending on the assay. After this period, all data is released publicly in accordance with FAIR data principles.

Figure 2 Step-by-step procedure for academic compound submission.

2.1.1 EACL compound collection workflow

The step-by-step procedure to collect academic compounds is detailed in Figure 2. To submit compounds to EU-OPENSREEN, interested researchers first contact the EU-OPENSREEN team by email at compound-submission@eu-openscreen.eu. Following this, a **Material Transfer Agreement (MTA)** is signed by the legal representative of the Institution and EU-OPENSREEN ERIC, outlining the terms of use, conditions, and data policies. Compound details are then submitted through the designated web application (<http://www.eu-openscreen-cmpds-donation.eu/login.php>) using provided credentials (Figure 1). The physical compounds are shipped to EU-OPENSREEN by the submitting chemist in **24-rack of 2D barcoded tubes** (ideally 5–10 mg per compound with at least 90% purity), with tubes provided by the CCMF. Once received by the CCMF team, the compounds are dissolved in DMSO, reformatted in 1ml tubes and transferred

⁴ <https://ecbd.eu/>

⁵ Ctibor Škuta, Tomáš Müller, Milan Voršilák, Martin Popr, Trevor Epp, Katholiki E Skopelitou, Federica Rossella, Bahne Stechmann, Philip Gribbon, Petr Bartůněk, **ECBD: European chemical biology database**, *Nucleic Acids Research*, 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae904>

into microplates before distributed to partner sites for **screening** and **bioprofiling**.

Each compound becomes part of the **European Academic Compound Library** (EACL) and undergoes biological profiling and will be tested against a wide range of biological and drug targets in the framework of EU-OPENSREEN user projects. Resulting data, including structure, quality control, bioprofiling, and bioactivity, is made publicly available in the ECBD after an embargo period. For any validated hits, EU-OPENSREEN actively supports collaboration between the original chemist and the assay provider to advance research.

2.1.2 Aim of deliverable 2.1

Building on the foundation laid by EU-OPENSREEN-DRIVE and the ongoing effort to enlarge the repository of academic compounds contributed by European and international chemists, this report provides an overview of the progress achieved during the first 18 months of the IMPULSE project. It highlights the acquisition of compounds across Europe through a network of ambassadors, their integration into the EACL, and the development of success user stories.

2.2 Description of work

2.2.1 Coordinated acquisition of compounds through recent ambassador activities

Established in 2019 within EU-OPENSREEN-DRIVE, the **Academic Library Working Group** brings together Ambassadors from EU-OPENSREEN ERIC member countries. Its mission is to engage local chemists by presenting the initiative at conferences, encourage compound submissions beyond current ERIC members, and broaden the geographic reach and impact of the library. The group is coordinated by the EU-OPENSREEN central office and the CCMF team (Phil Gribbon, Victoria Mora, David Garcia, Robert Harmel, and Bahne Stechmann). A full list of Ambassadors from 9 countries is provided in Table 1.

The academic library working group meets quarterly to discuss progress on the EACL, covering outreach activities, new compound acquisitions, available financial resources, and updates and feedback from ambassadors.

Table 1 List of EU-OPENSREEN ERIC ambassadors to promote the Academic Compounds Acquisition

Member Country	Name (Initials)	Affiliation (Abbreviation)
Czech Republic	Martin Popr (MP)	Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences (IMG)
Finland	Päivi Tammela (PT)	Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM)
Germany	Mark Brönstrup (MB)	Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research (HZI)
Latvia	Aigars Jirgensons (AJ)	Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis (LIOS)
Norway	Johannes Landskron (JL)	University of Oslo (UiO)
Poland	Zbigniew J. Leśnikowski (ZJL)	Institute of Medical Biology of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBM PAS)
Spain	Mabel Loza (ML)	University of Santiago de Compostela (USC)
Portugal	Antonio Pombinho (AP)	Institute for Molecular and Cell Biology (i3S)
Sweden	Anna-Lena Gustavsson (ALG)	Karolinska Institute (KI)

The ambassadors engage directly with chemists at the national level and serve as a link to the EU-OPENSSCREEN central office, which coordinates compound submissions and maintains the list of contributing chemists.

To facilitate alignment with national initiatives and foster synergies, ambassadors are working towards the integration of national compound collections (e.g., PL-OPENSSCREEN,⁶ ES-OPENSSCREEN) through framework agreements between EU-OPENSSCREEN and the respective owners of these collections. As part of this effort, the compound library submitted by national networks already includes 850 compounds from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), contributed through DK-OPENSSCREEN, with Denmark participating as a member country until 2023. Additional submissions from other national networks, such as Portugal are currently in preparation.

To raise awareness about the compound submission initiative and the benefits of contributing to the EACL, representatives of the academic library working group participated in numerous conferences and scientific events (Table 2). These activities not only promoted compound submissions but also helped expand the network of contributing chemists across Europe and beyond. Additional conferences are planned for 2025, with active participation, e.g., EFMC-ASMC 2025 (1–5 September, Porto, Portugal), New Trends in Chemistry Research 2025 (24–26 September, Timisoara, Romania), BrazMedChem 2025 (21 September, Búzios, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil) and ICBS/ECBS ChemBioParis 2025 (6–9 October, Paris, France).

Table 2 Major outreach and dissemination activities to promote the academic submission initiative from March 2024 until August 2025.

Date	Name	Place	Presentation type	Presenter	Affiliation
26.03.2024	Academic Compound Collection Initiative	Viikki campus, Helsinki, Finland	oral	PT	FIMM
23.04.2024	4th MMCS: Harnessing the Power of New Drug Modalities (MMCS2024)	Barcelona, Spain	oral	VM	EU-OS
14.05.2024	Viikki-Kumpula event	Helsinki, Finland	poster	PT	FIMM
05.06.2024	Canadian Chemistry Conference and Exhibition (CSC 2024)	Winnipeg, Canada	oral	BS	EU-OS
10.06.2024	CSBC2024- Chemical Solutions for Biological Challenges (CSBC2024)	Turku, Finland	oral	PT	FIMM
11.06.2024	Chemical Solutions to Biological Challenges 2024	Turku, Finland	oral	PT	FIMM
03.07.2024	58th edition of the International Conference on Medicinal Chemistry (RICT 2024)	Bordeaux, France	poster	VM	EU-OS

⁶ <https://pol-openscreen.pl/en/pol-openscreen-en/national-library-of-chemical-compounds/about-library/>

03.09.2024	International Symposium on Medicinal Chemistry (EFMC-ISMIC 2024)	Rome, Italy	poster	BS	EU-OS
19.11.2024	Finland national network meeting	Helsinki, Finland	oral	PT	FIMM
03.12.2024	IV POL-OPENSSCREEN Workshop	Lodz, Poland	oral	VM	EU-OS
09.01.2025	38 th Organic Chemistry Winter Meeting	Skeikampen, Norway	oral	JL	NOR-OS*
16.01.2025	COST Action EURESTOP-EUOS webinar	Online	oral	VM, RH	EU-OS
17.01.2025	International Think Tank for Preclinical Drug Discovery	Santiago Compostela, Spain	oral	PT, ML	FIMM, USC
21.02.2025	Encuentros 2025 Fundación Medina	Granada, Spain	oral	AG	USC
14.03.2025	Drug Discovery Africa 2025	Accra, Ghana	poster	TM	EU-OS
24.04.2025	Presentation Spanish Public Chemical Library	Barcelona, Spain	oral	AG	USC
28.04.2025	International Helmholtz Drug Discovery Conference (HDDC2025)	Berlin, Germany	oral	VM	EU-OS
09.05.2025	Presentation Spanish Public Chemical Library	San Sebastián, Spain	oral	AG	USC
12.05.2025	EU-OPENSSCREEN and ES-OPENSSCREEN workshop	Madrid, Spain	oral	VM	EU-OS
19.05.2025	Integrative Structural Biology meets Drug Discovery	Campinas, Brazil	oral	BS	EU-OS
20.05.2025	Society for Laboratory Automation and Screening (SLAS2025)	Hamburg, Germany	poster	VM	EU-OS
23.05.2025	Presentation Spanish Public Chemical Library	Valencia, Spain	oral	AG	USC
26.05.2025	Presentation Spanish Public Chemical Library	Badajoz, Spain	oral	AG	USC
16.06.2025	3rd National Meeting of the Swedish Chemical Society (SCS2025)	Västerås, Sweden	poster	AG	KI
11.06.2025	International Conference on Marine Bioprospecting (Bioprospect_25)	Tromso, Norway	oral	BS	EU-OS

15.06.2025	XXI National Meeting of the Spanish Society of Medicinal Chemistry (SEQT2025)	Sevilla, Spain	oral	VM	EU-OS
15.07.2025	IV Medicinal & Biological Chemistry Ireland Conference	Belfast, Ireland	oral	VM	EU-OS

*NOR-OS: NOR-OPENSSCREEN

2.2.2 Progress on the integration of academic compounds to the EACL from 1 March 2024 until 31 August 2025

The EACL has grown substantially since March 2024, with 7,481 compounds now stored at the CCMF in Berlin. These submissions originate from a total of 44 institutions across 17 countries, reflecting broad and steadily increasing international participation. Figure 3 presents the distribution of academic compounds collected per country during the EU-OPENSSCREEN-DRIVE project (2019–2023), highlighting the initial establishment of the library and the diversity of contributing partners. Figure 4 illustrates the sustained growth achieved under IMPULSE (2024–2025), presenting the number of academic compounds submitted per country since the project's launch in March 2024, totaling 1,944 additional compounds.

Figure 3 Academic compounds collected per country (2020–2023) within the EU-OPENSSCREEN-DRIVE project – total of 5,537 compounds.

Figure 4 Academic compounds collected per country (2024–2025) since the launch of the IMPULSE project in March 2024 – 1,944 compounds collected.

Since the launch of the IMPULSE project, WP2 has achieved several key milestones:

- 1,361 academic compounds were submitted in 2024, followed by 583 new submissions in 2025, bringing the number of compounds to **1,944** (7,481 overall), with 6,336 structures currently deposited in the ECBD.
- The geographic reach of the library has expanded significantly, with new submissions coming from **Portugal, Sweden, Slovenia, Chile, Costa Rica, and China**, broadening both European and international participation.
- **16 new Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs)** were signed, 6 of which in 2025 to date, with additional submissions expected later this year.
- Provision of compounds to partner sites remained consistent throughout IMPULSE: the first batch of 1,408 compounds was delivered in May 2024, followed by 704 compounds in January 2025, 352 in April 2025, and an additional 352 in August 2025.
- Since March 2024, additional **2,464 academic compounds** have undergone profiling including solubility testing, bioluminescence reporters, reactive oxygen species (ROS), cell viability, antibacterial and antifungal activity, and cell painting across multiple partner sites.
- Profiling data are being uploaded to the ECBD, facilitating data reuse and integration into future research initiatives. To date, a total of 5,984 academic compounds submitted to the EACL have been profiled, with the results accessible directly at ecbd.eu.

2.2.3 Success stories

To further increase the visibility of the compound submission initiative, EU-OPENSREEN has launched a dedicated webpage for the development of the European Academic Compound Library: <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/academic-library-development.html>.⁷

This webpage provides an overview of submitted compounds and ongoing bioprofiling activities and lists contributing institutions together with testimonials from submitters (Figure 5, left). It is regularly updated to reflect the growth of the collection, introduce new participants, and will increasingly serve to highlight success stories.

Going forward, success stories will form a central element of this initiative, which will be shared with the wider scientific community through scientific publications and targeted dissemination activities. They are designed to showcase that submitted compounds can lead to meaningful, tangible results. Following submission, compounds are tested in high-throughput screening (HTS) campaigns, where those showing promising biological activity are identified as primary hits. These hits are further validated in dedicated secondary assays to confirm potency. When biological activity is confirmed, a compound that was once solely a research product gains translational value – and this progression is captured and communicated as a success story (see Figure 5, right).

For submitting chemists, this offers multiple benefits, including greater visibility, new collaborations, and potential valorisation of their research, as recognised by chemists already contributing (see testimonials). For EU-OPENSREEN, it builds trust among existing contributors, raises the profile of the initiative, and helps attract new chemists. In this way, success stories clearly demonstrate the benefits of participation in the EACL while advancing EU-OPENSREEN's strategic goal of building trust and expanding its community of contributors.

Figure 5 Example of a testimonial of a chemist submitting academic compounds to the EACL from <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/academic-library-development.html> (left), overview of building a success story (right).

3 Conclusions/Next steps

In its first 18 months, WP2 has significantly advanced the European Academic Compound Library, expanding it to 7,481 compounds from 44 institutions across 17 countries. Outreach by ambassadors through presentations at major scientific conferences broadened the network, bringing in new countries, while 16 new MTAs and more than 2,000 compounds bioprofiled highlight strong scientific progress. A dedicated EACL webpage with testimonials and success stories has further increased visibility and impact.

To further expand the European Academic Compound Library, EU-OPENSREEN will continue to actively participate in several major conferences in 2025, including EFMC-ASMC (Porto, Portugal),

⁷ Detailed information on the compounds and their bioprofiling data can be accessed via <https://ecbd.eu/compound/> (academic compounds can be selected in the library window on the left).

New Trends in Chemistry Research (Timisoara, Romania), BrazMedChem (Búzios, Brazil), and ICBS/ECBS ChemBioParis (Paris, France). Building on this momentum, the Academic Library Working Group will prepare a dedicated conference strategy for 2026 to ensure continued visibility and engagement with the scientific community.

As part of these efforts, new chemists will be engaged and supported throughout the submission process. New submitted compounds will be reformatted at the CCMF in Berlin and distributed to partner sites for bioprofiling. In parallel, EU-OPENSSCREEN will implement a structured plan to streamline the bioprofiling of newly added compounds, ensuring systematic data integration into the ECBD and enabling broad reuse by the community.

EU-OPENSSCREEN will continue its strategy of developing success stories by selecting the most promising hits from the academic library for follow-up assays. These efforts are expected to lead to high-impact publications and presentations at upcoming conferences. In this way, EU-OPENSSCREEN aims to accelerate its scientific impact and inspire more chemists to join this collaborative initiative.

